

Energy Conservation Revisited: Generalized Laws and the Impact of Non-commutative and Non-Riemannian Geometries

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Abstract – This paper explores the impact of the Heisenberg Uncertainty Principle and noncommutative geometry on energy conservation, highlighting how these factors can lead to apparent violations of the classical energy conservation law. By incorporating approaches from non-Riemannian geometries, where *Bianchi's identity* does not hold in its traditional form, we propose a generalized law of energy conservation. This new law accounts for noncommutativity and quantum uncertainties, providing a more comprehensive framework for understanding energy conservation in the quantum realm. The paper discusses the theoretical foundations, mathematical formulation, and potential applications of this generalized conservation law.

Keywords: *Energy Conservation, Heisenberg Uncertainty Principle, Noncommutative Geometry, Non-Riemannian Geometry, Bianchi's Identity, Generalized Conservation Law.*

I. INTRODUCTION

Energy conservation is a fundamental concept in classical mechanics, asserting that the total energy of an isolated system remains constant over time. This principle is central to our understanding of physical processes and has been extensively studied within the framework of classical mechanics.

In Section II, we will review the classical formulation of energy conservation, including its mathematical basis and implications for various physical systems. As we move into the quantum realm, the Heisenberg Uncertainty Principle introduces new challenges to the traditional concept of energy conservation. This principle highlights fundamental limits on the precision of simultaneous measurements of certain physical quantities, such as energy and time.

Section III will explore the Heisenberg Uncertainty Principle, examining its impact on energy conservation and the adjustments required to account for quantum uncertainties. To address these challenges, we turn to noncommutative geometry in later sections, a mathematical framework where coordinates do not commute. This approach provides new perspectives on how quantum uncertainties can be integrated into the conservation laws.

In Section IV, we will delve into noncommutative geometry, discussing its definitions, key concepts, and how it modifies traditional notions of curvature and conservation. Next, we extend our exploration to non-Riemannian geometries, which include frameworks such as those with torsion geometries. These geometries provide alternative ways of describing space and curvature, where classical Bianchi identities may not directly apply.

Also, we will cover non-Riemannian geometries, highlighting how they differ from Riemannian geometries and the implications for conservation laws in these contexts. Building on the insights from noncommutative and non-Riemannian geometries.

Conclusion introduces a general overview law of energy conservation. This new formulation aims to reconcile the effects of noncommutativity and the unique features of non-Riemannian geometries with the principles of conservation. We will present the theoretical foundations, mathematical formulation, and potential applications of this generalized conservation law, offering a comprehensive framework for understanding energy conservation in both classical and quantum contexts. Through these sections, this paper aims to provide a detailed exploration of energy conservation, addressing its complexities and extending classical principles to accommodate the advancements in mathematical and physical theories.

II. CONSERVATION OF ENERGY IN CLASSICAL MECHANICS

Let $\mathcal{M}^{2n}$ be an even-dimensional differentiable manifold. A symplectic structure on $\mathcal{M}^{2n}$ is a closed, non-degenerate differential 2-form ω^2 on $\mathcal{M}^{2n}$, such that $d\omega^2 = 0$ and $(\forall \xi = 0)(\exists \mathbf{X}_H: \omega^2(\xi, \mathbf{X}_H) \neq 0)$ and $\xi, \mathbf{X}_H \in T\mathcal{M}_x$. This forms a $(\mathcal{M}^{2n}, \omega^2)$ symplectic manifold that can encode the structure of the phase space and the evolution of dynamical systems and ensure the conservation of the volume in phase space under the *Hamiltonian phase flows* $\varphi^t: \mathcal{M}^{2n} \rightarrow \mathcal{M}^{2n}$ where the Hamiltonian vector field $\mathbf{X}_H$ generates the flow.

Liouville's Theorem asserts that the volume form ω^n on a $2n$ -dimensional symplectic manifold $(\mathcal{M}, \omega)$ is preserved under the flow generated by a Hamiltonian vector field $\mathbf{X}_H$. Specifically, the Lie derivative of the volume form ω^n with respect to $\mathbf{X}_H$ is zero

$$\mathcal{L}_{\mathbf{X}_H}(\omega^n) = 0 \quad (2.1)$$

This result indicates that the volume in phase space remains invariant as the system evolves according to the Hamiltonian flow, reflecting the conservation of phase space volume in Hamiltonian mechanics. As a result, if we define H as first integral function of the Hamiltonian phase flow this implies the law of conservation of energy holds since $dH(\mathbf{X}_H) = \omega^2(\mathbf{X}_H, \cdot) = \omega^2(\mathbf{X}_H, \mathbf{X}_H) = 0$ as we define $dH/dt = \omega^2(\mathbf{X}_H, \mathbf{X}_H)$.

This result is always true under the conditions of the Hamiltonian mechanics. However, it may not necessarily hold true for non-Hamiltonian mechanics where additional forces or dissipative effects can cause the Hamiltonian to change over time. Let us redefine $\mathbf{X}_H$ to include an additional term we shall call $\mathbf{F}$ representing some certain effects,

$$\mathbf{X}_H = \mathbf{X}_H^{(0)} + \mathbf{F} \quad (2.2)$$

This definition requires modifications to the equations of motion for the system to account for the altered vector field $\mathbf{X}_H$.

$$\dot{q} = \{q, H\} + f_q(q, p, t) \quad (2.3)$$

$$\dot{p} = \{p, H\} + f_p(q, p, t) \quad (2.4)$$

Where f_q and f_p represent the additional forces or dissipative effects.

To see how this affects the conservation of H , we compute the time derivative of H along the new vector field $\mathbf{X}_H$, that is $dH/dt = dH(\mathbf{X}_H) = dH(\mathbf{X}_H^{(0)} + \mathbf{F})$, using the linearity property we get,

$$\frac{dH}{dt} = dH(\mathbf{X}_H^{(0)}) + dH(\mathbf{F}) \quad (2.4)$$

Since $dH(\mathbf{X}_H^{(0)}) = 0$, it reduces to

$$\frac{dH}{dt} - dH(\mathbf{F}) = 0 \quad (2.5)$$

This implies that $dH/dt \neq 0$, indicating that the total energy of the system is not conserved in the conventional sense. However, the overall energy is still conserved when accounting for external influences, as denoted by $dE_{\text{total}} := dH/dt - dH(\mathbf{F})$, Where $dH(\mathbf{F})$ represents the contribution to the energy change from external forces or dissipative effects.

We will follow the same approach to derive general modifications to energy conservation formulas so that we can maintain conservation and illustrate the limitations of each definition within its respective system. It is essential that we do not rely on the formulation *that energy is neither created nor destroyed but merely transformed from one form to another*, as this is incorrect within the system itself. However, it is valid in a broader context. If we define an S -system, therefore the indicator is time – dependent $\mathbb{I}_S(t)$,

$$\mathbb{I}_S(t) = \begin{cases} 1, dH(\mathbf{F}_t) \in S \\ 0, dH(\mathbf{F}_t) \notin S \end{cases} \quad (2.6)$$

If we assume that the contribution is non-zero at time $t > 0$, then $dH(\mathbf{F}_{t=0}) \notin S$ and $dH(\mathbf{F}_{T \in (0, \infty)}) \in S$, this implies within the system itself the energy is not conserved as the environment is undefined for the S -system. For example, consider a point mass m connected to a spring with a force constant k , where the opposite end of the spring is attached to a massless cart. This cart is being moved uniformly by an external device at a constant speed v_0 . If we choose the position x of the mass particle in the stationary system as the generalized coordinate, the Hamiltonian of the system is clearly,

$$H(x, p, t) = \frac{p^2}{2m} + \frac{k}{2}(x - v_0 t)^2 \quad (2.7)$$

In Equation 2.7, it is evident that when finding the Hamiltonian with respect to time, it will not equal zero. This means that, within the system itself, it gains

energy, indicating that from the system's own perspective, it does not conserve total energy internally. However, the gained energy results from other physical effects, which may not necessarily be transferred energy in classical sense, but rather the influence of other physical quantities upon which the energy somehow depends. We regard energy as a non-independent physical quantity that responds to the system's own constraints. We might consider that energy can appear from nothing simply because the nature of the system permits this. In such cases, we generalize the law of energy conservation by acknowledging that even "nothing" itself has effects through which total energy increases or decreases. For instance, similar to how the geometry of a water hose and the flow velocity interact, where the flow speed increases as the cross-sectional area decreases, if the geometry involved in energy matters provides a nonconservative field, it implies that within this field, the total energy is not constant. Instead, there are other effects causing the energy to increase. We call this a *contribution*, which we can consider as the environment. This will be our approach to generalizing the conservation of energy as it can be seen in equation 2.5.

III. ENERGY CONSERVATION IN THE CONTEXT OF THE UNCERTAINTY PRINCIPLE

The Heisenberg Uncertainty Principle is relevant to pairs of observables that do not commute, indicating that their measurements are intrinsically connected in a manner that generates uncertainty. This relationship is mathematically expressed through the commutation relation between the operators representing these observables. A quantum system is defined as a triple $(\mathcal{H}, \mathcal{A}, t \mapsto U_t)$, where $\mathcal{H}$ is a separable complex Hilbert space, $\mathcal{A}$ is a von Neumann algebra of linear operators on $\mathcal{H}$, and U_t is a strongly continuous one-parameter unitary representation in $\mathcal{A}$ of the group $\mathbb{R}$ under addition. The Hilbert space represents a collection of states; the algebra comprises operators that represent observables; and the unitary representation describes the system's dynamics. According to Stone's theorem, there exists a unique self-adjoint operator $H \in \mathcal{A}$ (the 'energy' operator or 'Hamiltonian') such that the dynamics are expressed as $(\forall t \in \mathbb{R})(U_t = \exp(iHt))$, where U_t is a unitary propagator.

A set of operators $\{A_\lambda\} \in \mathcal{A}$ parameterized by a real number λ where one specific value corresponds to the correct or physically real operator of interest:

$$A_\lambda = A_0 + V_\lambda \quad (3.1)$$

As $\lambda \rightarrow 0$, $V_\lambda \rightarrow 0$, and A_0 is called the *unperturbed operator*, and 3.1 can be approximated to a linear form, using the expansion leads to,

$$A_\lambda = A_0 + \lambda V + \mathcal{O}(\lambda^2) \quad (3.2)$$

Where $V := \frac{d}{d\lambda} V|_{\lambda=0} \equiv H - H_0$, the apparent violation of the law of energy conservation is deduced via considering higher-order terms approximation, that is due to the fact that interacting systems with the $[H_0, V] \neq 0$ the unperturbed Hamiltonian is not stationary $[H, H_0] \neq 0$. We may use a measure theory approach to determine the total energy in a system by summing up the energy contributions from all subsets. This involves modeling the energy distribution with a measure known as the energy measure. First, define the system of interest and the corresponding measure space. Let S be the system, and consider a measure space (S, Σ, μ) , where S is the set representing the system, Σ is a σ -algebra of subsets of S , and μ is a measure on Σ . Next, we introduce the energy measure μ_E , which quantifies the energy distribution within the system. For any subset A in Σ , $\mu_E(A)$ indicates the amount of energy in that subset. If you consider a system S with an energy measure μ_E and subsets $\{A_i\} \subseteq S$, the subadditivity principle ensures that,

$$\mu_E\left(\bigcup_{i \in I} A_i\right) \leq \mu_E\left(\sum_{i \in I} A_i\right) \quad (3.3)$$

If we define $\bigcup_{i \in I} A_i = S$ then,

$$\mu_E(S) \leq \mu_E\left(\sum_{i \in I} A_i\right) \quad (3.4)$$

The inequality in 3.4 can indicate the conservation of energy if we assume that $\{A_{i \in I}\}$ are mutually exclusive, therefore 3.4 can be exactly, $\mu_E(S) = \mu_E(\sum_{i \in I} A_i)$. But in the general case in 3.4, the energy appears not to be conserved. We need to refine this by only considering an arbitrary function $\mu_{\text{vio}}(A_{i \in I})$ that can represent the interactions; therefore, we obtain the general equality of 3.4,

$$\mu_E(S) = \mu_E\left(\sum_{i \in I} A_i\right) \pm \mu_{\text{vio}}(A_{i \in I}) \quad (3.5)$$

Therefore, we can claim that 3.4 agrees with the result, $[H, H_0] \neq 0$, however we can add μ_{vio} into our consideration, then $[H', H_0] = 0$, where H' is the new Hamiltonian of the system S .

We can consider another approach (See figure 1) Assume that there exists a set $S_E = \{\mu_E(x_E); x_E \in \mathbb{R}^n\}$ containing points x_E , which are spatial points that contains finite energy $\mu_E(x_E)$, we will refer to as *energy points*. This system S has a total sum of its elements equal to a constant denoted as $\mathcal{E}$. Furthermore, let us assume that the system S includes its limit points, which can be described by the following set definition: $L_p = \{x_E \in \mathbb{R}^n; \exists \{\mu_E(x_E)\} \subseteq S: \mu_E(x_{E_k}) \rightarrow \mu(x)|_{k \rightarrow \infty}\}$.

Figure 1: It illustrates a system S with its environment $\bar{S}$

If we assume that the system is *dynamically static*, meaning the total sum of its energy points is constant, this implies that the system S_E is an *open* system that exchanges energy, as its elements have changed over time. If we assume that points are isolated, then the sum can be written as,

$$\mathcal{E} = \sum_{x_E \in S} x_E \quad (3.6)$$

Since the system is dynamically static that means when we change $L_p \rightarrow L'_p$, the whole set changes $S_E \rightarrow S'_E$, and $S \subset S'$, therefore,

$$\sum_{x_E \in S'} x_E = \sum_{x_E \in S} x_E \quad (3.7)$$

In fact, the equation 3.7 is true when $\sum_{x_E \in (S' \setminus S)} x_E = 0$ meaning the added points should not contribute to the total energy of the system. Considering *Heisenberg-Robertson Uncertainty* relation for simplicity, we shall define $\forall x \in L_p$ is an operator. Let $\phi(x)$ be an arbitrary wave function, therefore,

$$(\forall x \in L_p)[\hat{H}, \hat{x}]\phi = -\frac{i\hbar}{2m}(\hat{p}\phi) \quad (3.8)$$

And hence,

$$\sigma_H \sigma_{x \in L_p} \geq \frac{\hbar}{2m} |\langle p \rangle| \quad (3.9)$$

Since there is uncertainty in all values of L_p , this implies that the system randomly adds or removes energy points. This is consistent with the assumption that the system is open, and under these conditions, it cannot be considered isolated. Therefore, to adhere to the law of conservation of energy, we need to explain that these changes do not affect the total energy of the system, which is what we are attempting to explore. It is evident that we can express the Hamiltonian in terms of the energy points as follows,

$$\forall x_E \in S_p \left(H(x_E, t) = \int_{S_p(t)} d^n x \varrho(x_E, t) \right) \quad (3.10)$$

Where $S_p = \{x_E; x_E \in \mathbb{R}^n, x_E \in L_p\}$, taking the derivative of 3.10 gives,

$$\frac{d}{dt} H(x_E, t) = \int_{S_p(t)} d^n x \partial_t \varrho(x_E, t) + \xi(x_E, t) \quad (3.11)$$

Where $\xi(x_E, t) = \int_{\partial S_p(t)} \varrho(x_E, t) (\mathbf{v} \cdot \mathbf{n}) d\sigma$, this result is obtained by applying Leibniz rule for higher dimensions. If we let $\partial_t \varrho(x_E, t) = 0$ then 3.11 tells us that the system without considering the effects of the uncertainty $\xi(x_E, t) = 0$, this gives $dH/dt = 0$, which indicates that system is at least dynamically static. However, the total energy in the system is not conserved within the system itself, we can therefore go straight to the generalized conservation law,

$$\frac{d}{dt} H(x_E, t) - \xi(x_E, t) = 0 \quad (3.12)$$

This does not guarantee that the system is dynamically static, but it tells us that the energy is always conserved. We can see that the law of conservation of energy can be reinterpreted to account for conditions under which the system itself is not energy-conserving. As demonstrated in Section II, we found that in classical mechanics, under the influence of an external environment, the energy of the system itself may not be conserved. However, overall, we found that energy is always conserved in the sense that the increase within the system equals the decrease in the environment, and vice versa. It is important to note that the **environment** need not be defined solely in terms of forces. Rather, the environment can be more broadly defined as any set of variables $v \in V$ as V is the of all possible variables, such that, $\phi_{\text{Env}} = \{v; v \in V\}$ that a physical system can rely upon, whether these influences are internal or external to the system, $\phi_{\text{Sys}} = \{w; w = f(v), v \in \phi_{\text{Env}}\}$.

IV. THE LAW OF CONSERVATION OF ENERGY UNDER THE NON-COMMUTATIVE AND NON-RIEMANNIAN GEOMETRIES

In General Theory of Relativity (GTR), we can demonstrate that energy is conserved in any four-dimensional Riemannian space. This can be achieved by utilizing Bianchi's identity or by employing a Killing vector. By using Bianchi's identity,

$$R_{\beta\gamma\delta;\epsilon}^{\gamma} + R_{\beta\epsilon\gamma;\delta}^{\gamma} + R_{\beta\delta\epsilon;\gamma}^{\gamma} = 0 \quad (4.1)$$

Which leads to,

$$\partial_{\epsilon} R_{\beta\delta} - \partial_{\delta} R_{\beta\epsilon} + \partial_{\gamma} R_{\beta\delta\epsilon}^{\gamma} = 0 \quad (4.2)$$

Finally contracting and introducing the *Ricci tensor* gives,

$$\partial_{\beta} G^{\alpha\beta} = 0 \quad (4.3)$$

Where $G^{\alpha\beta}$ is the *Einstein tensor*, and 4.3 leads directly to $\nabla_{\beta} T^{\alpha\beta} = 0$ which indicates the conservation law. It is valid for any General Relativity spacetime. However, there are numerous models that do not yield the same result, and they may suggest that the divergence of the *stress-energy tensor* is not zero. According to its classical definition, this would imply that energy is not conserved as defined by equation 4.3. Therefore, we can address this issue by simply assuming that the stress-energy tensor does not reduce to zero and explore the abstract possibilities that arise from this assumption. We can then proceed to examine some existing examples. We first let $\nabla_{\nu} T^{\mu\nu} = \kappa \Lambda^{\mu}$, where κ is a constant for the consistency of the equation, and Λ^{μ} is an array, for simplicity we set $\Lambda^1 = \Lambda^2 = \Lambda^3 = 0$ and therefore, $\nabla_{\nu} T_{\mu=1,2,3}^{\mu\nu} = 0$. We are interested in $\nabla_{\nu} T^{0\nu} = \kappa \Lambda^0$, and for further simplification, assume $T^{\mu\nu}$ is symmetry, hence, if $\nabla_{\nu} T^{\mu\nu} = \partial_{\nu} T^{\mu\nu} + \Gamma_{\sigma\nu}^{\mu} T^{\sigma\nu} + \Gamma_{\sigma\nu}^{\nu} T^{\mu\sigma} = \kappa \Lambda^{\mu}$, therefore it can be rewritten as follows,

$$\partial_0 T^{00} + \Gamma_{\sigma\nu}^0 T^{\sigma\nu} + \Gamma_{\sigma\nu}^{\nu} T^{0\sigma} = \kappa \Lambda^0 \quad (4.4)$$

Under these assumptions, the term $\Gamma_{\sigma\nu}^0 T^{\sigma\nu}$ is equivalent to $\Gamma_{00}^0 T^{00}$ and the term $\Gamma_{\sigma\nu}^{\nu} T^{0\sigma}$ is also equivalent to the expression, $\Gamma_{0\nu}^{\nu} T^{00}$, then we can rewrite 4.4 as follows,

$$\partial_0 T^{00} + (\Gamma_{00}^0 + \Gamma_{0\nu}^{\nu}) T^{00} = \kappa \Lambda^0 \quad (4.5)$$

We now have a first-order differential equation, which can be solved as a linear first order Ordinary Differential Equation (ODE). While the result might be too idealistic to observe, it serves merely as an approximation to emphasize the concept of generalized energy conservation. Let us assume the initial conditions to be such that the spacetime contains only an initial energy distribution at time $t = 0$. Consequently, the solution to the equation will simply be,

$$T^{00} = \frac{\kappa \Lambda^0}{\Gamma_{00}^0 + \Gamma_{0\nu}^{\nu}} (1 - e^{-(\Gamma_{00}^0 + \Gamma_{0\nu}^{\nu})t}) + \zeta(t) \quad (4.6)$$

Where $\zeta(t) = \rho_E e^{-(\Gamma_{00}^0 + \Gamma_{0\nu}^{\nu})t}$, this suggests as $t \rightarrow \infty$ the energy $T^{00} \rightarrow \kappa \Lambda^0 / (\Gamma_{00}^0 + \Gamma_{0\nu}^{\nu})$, if the energy is conserved under the Riemannian Geometry, therefore it will be $T^{00} \rightarrow 0$ instead. To evaluate the entropy $S(t)$ associated with the given energy-momentum tensor component $T^{00}(t)$, we proceed by first considering the total energy $E(t)$ within a fixed volume V . This energy is given by $E(t) = VT^{00}(t)$ —a special case—also we assume that T which is the temperature is related to energy in a fixed volume such that $T \propto E^{1/4}(t)$ which means,

$$T(t) = \alpha \sqrt[4]{\frac{\kappa \Lambda^0}{\Gamma_{00}^0 + \Gamma_{0\nu}^{\nu}} (1 - e^{-(\Gamma_{00}^0 + \Gamma_{0\nu}^{\nu})t}) + \zeta(t)} \quad (4.7)$$

Evaluating the equation 4.7 in $\Delta S(t) = \int_0^t \frac{1}{T} \frac{dE(t')}{dt'} dt'$ gives,

$$\Delta S = \int_0^t \frac{\kappa \Lambda^0 - \rho_E (\Gamma_{00}^0 + \Gamma_{0\nu}^{\nu})}{T(t') e^{(\Gamma_{00}^0 + \Gamma_{0\nu}^{\nu})t'}} dt' \quad (4.8)$$

Figure 2: For some values of Γ_{00}^0 and $\Gamma_{0\nu}^{\nu}$, the system can avoid the thermal death. (GeoGebra)

It becomes evident that when $t \rightarrow \infty$, entropy also depends on the geometry of spacetime itself over a certain range through Christoffel symbols.

Some values lead to a thermal death of that region, while other values cause it to continue increasing indefinitely. In Figure 2, a graph illustrates the case where entropy increases from a given time to infinity, without reaching a maximum value. This suggests that thermal death is avoided in this scenario. However, we assumed that the total energy within the system is not conserved, indicating that the system is not closed, which aligns with our proposed analysis. Although the system may not be closed, this does not undermine the validity of the law of energy conservation for the system. As is customary, we can assert that the increase in the system's energy under the influence of non-Riemannian geometry is equal to the contribution of this geometry to the total energy of the system. We can state that,

$$\nabla_\nu T^{\mu\nu} - \kappa\Lambda^\mu = 0 \quad (4.9)$$

Riemannian geometry fundamentally relies on the metric tensor, which is a symmetric, positive-definite matrix that defines the geometric properties of a space, such as distances and angles, and is used to calculate curvature and other geometric quantities. If the metric tensor deviates from these properties, such as being indefinite or not positive-definite, it characterizes a different geometric framework. For instance, in pseudo-Riemannian geometry, the metric can be indefinite, as seen in general relativity, leading to different causal structures. Other non-Riemannian geometries, such as Finsler geometry, involve metrics dependent on both position and direction, or affine geometry, which focuses on properties invariant under affine transformations without defining distances. Additionally, noncommutative geometry treats coordinates as noncommuting variables, extending the concept of geometry to include algebraic structures. Therefore, the choice of metric determines whether the geometry is Riemannian or falls into another geometric category.

Choosing a non-standard Riemannian or a non-Riemannian Geometry will not preserve $\nabla_\nu T^{\mu\nu} = 0$, we are going to show some examples in which a system undergoes a non-zero divergence. For a non-commutative Riemannian we can obtain the divergence $\nabla_\nu T^{\mu\nu} \neq 0$ in our special case. Considering the matter distribution, $\rho(v, r) = m(v)e^{-r^2/4\theta}/(4\pi\theta)^{3/2}$,

$$\partial_0 T^{00} - \frac{r^2\theta - 2}{16\pi^{3/2}r\theta^{3/2}} \underbrace{m(v)e^{-r^2\theta/4}}_{\kappa\Lambda^0} = 0 \quad (4.10)$$

This result aligns with the general thesis we are presenting: that within the framework of non-standard Riemannian geometry, or in this case, non-commutative

Riemannian geometry, the total energy within a given system does not approach zero. However, by defining the nature of the surrounding environment, the system does not become isolated. Instead, the geometry is a variable belonging to the set of variables associated with the environment. Thus, energy does not arise from pure nothingness.

In Cartan's theory, where a general affine connection is used instead of the Levi-Civita connection from Riemannian geometry, the divergence of the stress-energy tensor $T^{\mu\nu}$ is given by the expression involving the partial derivatives of the tensor components and terms related to the affine connection. Specifically, the divergence is calculated as the partial derivative of $T^{\mu\nu}$ with respect to the coordinates, plus contributions from the affine connection terms $\Gamma_{\mu\lambda}^\mu T^{\lambda\nu}$ and $\Gamma_{\mu\lambda}^\nu T^{\mu\lambda}$. It only satisfies $\nabla_\nu T^{\mu\nu} = 0$ with the absence of torsions.

V. CONCLUSION

In conclusion, this paper introduces a comprehensive overview of a generalized law of energy conservation. This new formulation seeks to reconcile the effects of noncommutativity and the distinctive features of non-Riemannian geometries with the principles of conservation. By addressing the complexities of energy conservation and extending classical principles to incorporate recent advancements in mathematical and physical theories, this paper aims to offer a thorough exploration and enhancement of the concept of energy conservation.

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